

Do Not Cling to Me!

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Do not cling to me! Are you a proponent of social distancing or detachment? Social distancing is the magic mantra to be recited and put into practice. As the Easter season approaches how are we to make sense of the lockdown? This year's Lent will be an unforgettable Lent for the Christian world, heavily loaded with fear and anxiety, deeply charged with emotions- the grief, the sorrow and the utter helplessness. The lockdown offers a forced withdrawal from the consumeristic-world, spirit leading us into the desert as it were. Not much to consume except the **online content**. Most of us are clueless as to how to spend the lockdown period. Having to do nothing is so annoying and distressing; just being and not doing anything was not that easy. Confined to a room could be a claustrophobic experience leading to boredom and frustration. With ever swelling surge in Covid-19 cases the lockdown may extend, and that's the worry of most of the Indians. The Easter season may look like an extended Lenten season. Can we cull out something from the resurrection accounts to make sense of the lockdown?

Mary Magdalene

In the scriptures, Mary Magdalene is first to witness the resurrection of Jesus. Mary turns twice- a turn within the turn (Jn 20: 14, 16)- to the one who calls while she was frantically looking for Jesus. The Lockdown was the first turn we made but the second turn is a deeper turn inviting us to a personal conversion to embrace a new life. The

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embrace is natural once the Lord reveals himself to us, as he did to Mary. When Mary recognized her Rabbouni she tried to cling to Jesus, but Jesus told her not to cling on to him. 'Do not cling to me' is a change of focus, Jesus is pointing towards his mystical body. Jesus redirects Mary's desire for union with himself from his physical or earthly body to the new locus of his presence in the world, that is, the

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community of his brothers and sisters, the disciples. In other words, we need to place ourselves at the tomb – the finality of affliction and suffering- in order to experience the power of resurrection. For our times it would be to search for the Lord hysterically like Mary, , in homeless, the destitute, the migrant, the poor, and in the afflicted. Being quarantined too could be seen as a greater mission to stop the further spread of the disease. Social distancing is another tool at our disposal to contain the spread and be united in spirit with the physicians, experts, health care workers, police personnel and the administration. Thus, alleviating the pressure on the health care system. The encounter with the Lord ought to fill us with Easter joy and peace. The peace that the risen Lord offers is a pre-requisite for reception of the holy spirit. We are duty-bound to give the peace of the Lord to those in trouble and tribulation due to corona-crisis. The encounter of the risen Lord is profoundly transformative, it dispels fear and anxiety. Mary's encounter with the risen Lord tells us that God wants us to be with the community of faithful and announce the good-news to the afflicted and cling to the mystical body of Christ. Social

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distancing is not to be understood as saving oneself but saving the community.

The Emmaus

The lockdown, with lurking uncertainty, can really sap our energy leaving us empty and dissatisfied. The anxiety and disappointment too can overpower us like the two disciples walking to Emmaus. We are not alone on this journey of war against Corona there is risen Jesus who walks along (often as stranger) we just need to be vigilant as to know what burns our heart and what sets our heart ablaze. As Jesus walks with us he waits for our invitation to dine with us. Even in that hour of frustration and utter hopelessness the disciples did dare to share what they had with the stranger. The sharing, breaking of the bread, open their eyes to recognize the presence of Jesus. At this hour of pandemic, we too need to share with the strangers and needy and have that experience of experiencing the risen Lord. The disciples would have loved to remain in that union at the breaking of bread but the Lord disappears; perhaps he does not want us to cling to him. Rather, like the disciples wants us to rush to the community to announce the good news. The disciples who were disappointed and had lost hope in Jesus, were filled with hope again with the mission to proclaim the gospel of the Lord.

The Early Christians

As the scripture says the early Christians lacked nothing because they shared all that they had with the community. Tertullian wrote that while pagan temples spent their donations “on feasts and drinking bouts,” Christians spent theirs “to support and bury poor people, to supply the wants of boys and girls destitute of means and parents, and of old persons confined to the house.” The Christ who

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shared/sacrificed his life was the sole inspiration of the early Christians. Their sharing was frowned upon; for they were overwhelmingly selfless.

Eucharist was another occasion of sharing, though the eucharists were not as often as we have. They were once in a while and needed a lot of preparation. The eucharist would sustain their faith till the next. There are no masses during lockdown period, more or less the same situation as the early Christians under persecution. Though we have the luxury of watching the mass being celebrated but cannot consume the consecrated species. It's been almost a month we are without the eucharist. It's our testing time to see how deep are the waters of our faith. Moreover, the Quarantined period poses a challenge of living the eucharist. Breaking our body for the other, the suffering other is the call of this year's Easter. One needs to undergo the passion of Christ in order make sense of Jesus' resurrection. Let's be the Passover that redeems the suffering humanity. There's no greater love than to lay down one's life for the other.

Can we say that “**I have seen the Lord**” in the suffering other, in poor, migrant workers, daily wagers, and the lonely elderly crowd as we distance ourselves from the people? The command of Jesus is to not cling to him but to cling to his mystical body.

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